

Femto-second laser processing in Boro-Aluminosilicate Glass – a technology platform for the combination of mechanical structures and integrated waveguides

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ABSTRACT

3D printing in glass has experienced a significant boost in the last few years and has established itself in research and industry as a manufacturing process for micro-components. We present a novel technology platform which enables the integration of optical waveguides and mechanical structures in boro-aluminosilicate glass. The manufacturing process uses an ultra-short pulse laser to inscribe the optical waveguide and to micromachine the geometry.

KEYWORDS: laser bulk micromachining, optical waveguide, boro-aluminosilicate glass, 3D glass printing

INTRODUCTION

Selective laser induced etching (SLE) was originally developed for fused silica (FS) [1], due to the high selectivity of up to 1000 that can be achieved. This high selectivity allows high precision fabrication of 3D microdevices in glass for various applications, like microfluidics, micromechanics and optics. Femto-second laser treatment of glass can not only be used for 3D structuring, but also for the fabrication of integrated waveguides. The ultra-short laser pulses lead to material modifications, generating a local refractive index change in the glass. For fused silica this refractive index change is quite small. The highest reported refractive index contrast we found is $\Delta n \sim 5E-3$ [2].

In boro-aluminosilicate glass (Corning® Eagle XG®) a refractive index contrast of $\Delta n \sim 9E-3$ to $17E-3$ can be achieved [3]. This enables better mode confinement and allows tighter radii of curvature for single-mode waveguides. Laser-written waveguides make 3D waveguide routing possible, which is required for the fabrication of 3D splitters or interferometers [2, 4]. A selective laser induced etching process for boro-aluminosilicate glass was first reported by Memeo et. al [5], where they achieved laser writing speeds of up to 2 mm/s and an etch selectivity of about 60 in KOH. In order to economically fabricate mechanical functional elements in Eagle XG, this speed must be increased.

Based on a systematic parameter study, a process window with higher writing speeds and a comparable selectivity for Corning® Eagle XG® was found. To demonstrate the potential of boro-aluminosilicate glass for the combination of waveguides and mechanical structures, we present a novel design of a flexure ring with an integrated optical waveguide.

PROCESS DEVELOPMENT

Bulk Micromachining in boro-aluminosilicate glass

In order to optimize the patterning of the glass by SLE, we performed a parameter study with the intention of maximizing the writing speed while ensuring the highest possible selectivity of the etching process. For this purpose, lines were inscribed under the surface at different laser parameters and different writing speeds. These lines were subsequently etched and characterized. Fig. 1 shows the etched lines for a writing speed of 50 mm/s. The maximum observed etch rate r_1 is in the range of 9 to $14.5 \mu\text{m/h}$. Considering the etch rate of the unmodified material ($r_0 = 0.25 \mu\text{m/h}$) the selectivity for a writing speed of 50 mm/s is in the range of 35 to 60.

Figure 1: Wet chemical etched laser treated lines (speed 50 mm/s, laser wavelength 1030 nm, pulse duration 5 ps, repetition rate 50 kHz, different laser pulse energies) after 72 h etching in hot potassium hydroxide (8 mol/l, 80°C)

Waveguide writing in boro-aluminosilicate glass

Corning® Eagle XG® is widely used as a substrate material for the fabrication of laser-written integrated waveguides due to the relatively high refractive index contrast generated by laser-induced material modifications. Our single-mode waveguides at the wavelength 1550 nm have a gradient index profile (Fig. 2a) and show propagation losses of 0.15 dB/cm. The critical bending radius was found to be 15 mm (Fig. 2b).

Figure 2: a) refractive index profile and image of the cross section of a WG inscribed by a laser wavelength 1030 nm, rep. rate of 1MHz, pulse duration of 300 fs, pulse energy of ~ 200 nJ and speed of 4 mm/s. b) Curvature dependent loss of arc-based s-bends

THE FLEXURE RING DEVICE

The manufacturing process for the flexure ring device consists of five main production steps (Fig. 3a). First, the waveguides are written into the substrate. In the next step the geometry of the flexure ring is structured by a combination of laser treatment and subsequent wet chemical etching. For the first and second step the same laser setup is used without repositioning of the substrate to ensure the best possible alignment between waveguides and mechanical structure. Finally, two post processing steps are used to improve the side wall roughness and to package optical fibers with the opto-mechanical waveguide device.

Figure 3: a) Illustration of the manufacturing process flow; b) Final demonstrator of a mechanical flexure ring with an integrated helical waveguide loop

The demonstrator in Fig. 3b consists of a mechanical flexure with an inscribed helical waveguide loop. The flexure consists of a ring and a bending beam to improve the stiffness of the system. In the ring a three-dimensional routed helical waveguide with one loop is inscribed. If the bending beam and the ring are deflected, the waveguide will be deformed.

CONCLUSIONS

We have introduced an optical-mechanical waveguide system fully integrated in glass. The platform enables the integration of 3D waveguides and 3D mechanical structures in a single substrate. Moreover, all elements are written with the same laser, ensuring high precision between waveguides and mechanics. The new technology platform potentially enables applications in the fields of packaging and sensor technology.

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